

Impact of Nitrogen Application on Wheat (*Triticum Aestivum L.*) Growth Stages and Yield

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Abstract

Efficient application of Nitrogen is an important aspect for economic purpose and protection of ground and surface water from nitrogen depletion. Absorption of more nitrogen cause lodging and disease attack as resulted in decreasing of yield and more inputs application cost. However, improper nitrogen application cause yield loss and ultimately loss of economic profits as compared to properly applied nitrogen. Application timing and dose are the major aspects of getting maximum wheat production. Nitrogen impacts on grain size, sq. ft and grains/head. Nitrogen fertilizer effect the grain protein percentage that is important for baking purposes. There is a proper dose of nitrogen application in wheat growth that determines crop quality and yield. Nitrogen plays an important role in rapid growth, leaf development, and size, green leaf duration, tiller formation, increase grain protein, grain size, and grain quality. The purpose of literature is analyzing the impact of nitrogen on wheat crop.

Keywords: Nitrogen use efficiency, wheat growth stages, Yield production.

1. Introduction:

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum L.*) is the one of the main cereal crop cultivated to feed the humans in the world. It is cultivated around 100 million hectares in the world. Worldwide wheat is cultivated in Australia, Canada, China, India, Pakistan, Russia, Turkey and united states that contribute 80 percent of the world production (FAO, 2007). Wheat contained largest cultivated area as compared to other field crops. (Ei Hwary & Yagoub, 2011). The utilization of nitrogen is very low in winter dormancy, if applied in this stage it will leach down or run-off from the root zone of the crop. Application of proper nutrients is necessary to get high yield from a crop. Mostly nitrogen used by grain transferred from the stem, leaves, and head rather than from soil. However, if these elements are not properly applied on specifically required stage, ultimately nutrients efficiency and yield will be minimized. The timing and dose of any nutrient depend on crop type, variety, climate conditions, soil characteristics, and management practices. The combination of these factors influences nutrients requirements, nutrient composition, and overall production. The time and dose of Nitrogen is the main step to enhance efficiency. Application timing is important because nutrition should be available to plant when it requires for growth and quantity is necessary to fulfill the desired nutrients to crop. A small quantity of nitrogen in necessary for early seedling vigor growth. High dose may cause damage of seedling, over vegetative growth in the early season with depletion of soil moisture contents. (Jones, Rutz, & Dinkins, 2015) Excessive dose of nitrogen may effect on tiller formation, crop growth, seed protein percentage and delay crop maturity period. Application timing and quantity varies with region to region. Nitrogen uptake is different with different growth stages. So, we will discuss the overall impacts of nitrogen in wheat. Globally, increasing population demand more food and protein needs that is possible with proper management and efficient application of inputs The utilization of nitrogen is increasing as synthetic nitrogen in 1990 was only 9.2 Mt; it increased in 1995 to 80.4 Mt and recently in 2015 it was 108 Mt recorded. (Christian, Uwe , & Malcolm J., 2018). In the world, Nitrogen use efficiency scale is 47 percent and for some decades in cereals is 33 percent. (Christian, Uwe , & Malcolm J., 2018). There are main three growth stages of wheat that demand more nitrogen as compared to other stages. The seed contains 6mg of total protein that is enough for germination and seedling until the first leaf did not emerge. Nitrogen plays an important role in tillers formation. So, proper nitrogen management is important to increase nitrogen use efficiency and to attain high yield.

2. Effect of Nitrogen on wheat yield production

Nitrogen plays an important role in yield production and necessary for protein contents in grains. The literature showed that the nitrogen composition of wheat increased with increasing of Nitrogen fertilizer application. (Xue, et al., 1 June, 2016). Fertilizer management plays an efficient role on baking quality of flour by effecting composition and concentration of gluten protein and polymerization. Environmental conditions and water are also important aspects of storage proteins. (Savil, Michalski, Power, Wan, & Hawkesford, 25 May 2018). Increasing the dose of nitrogen in 13 varieties did not impact on amount and composition of albumins and globulins, but the composition of w-gliadins and HMW-GS enhances. (H. Wieser & Seilmeier, 1998). Wheat crop is sensitive to nitrogen deficient availability and gives a very positive response to proper nitrogen fertilization. The main function of nitrogen is its involvement in protein structure and building substance from which protoplasm of every cell is made. Nitrogen is also found in chlorophyll contents and green leaves. So, green leaves able to make energy from sunlight by photosynthesis. Therefore, application of nitrogen is essential for the protein, protoplasm and chlorophyll formation, and yield production. To check the effect of different doses of nitrogen application in wheat, MONSANTO conducted research at Gothenburg, NE. The site soil was hord silt loam, dryland soil, five varieties, planting time- November 10, 2016, the previous crop was soybean, Soil Ph -6.6, Organic Matter 4%, residual nitrogen -37 lbs./ acre and Phosphorus -40ppm/. Nitrogen dose were 0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 lbs./acre. Fig. 1 is showing the results of different doses application in wheat. (Monsanto, 2017)

Fig. 1. Effect of different nitrogen rates on wheat yield (Monsanto, 2017)

The results clearly show the effect of different rates of nitrogen application on yield of wheat. Therefore, application of nitrogen is essential for the protein, protoplasm and chlorophyll formation, and yield production. The growth of the plant with nitrogen application became fast and remained leaves green for photosynthesis. Improper nitrogen availability results in light green color, minimize tillers formation, effect on cell growth distribution, protein percentage in grain and ultimately yield loss. Optimum application dose is essential otherwise with high dose it causes dark green color, high growth that will cause of lodging, increase crop duration and more chances of diseases (rust, Septoria, and powdery mildew) and pest attack. (Cutts, 2010).

3. Nitrogen management for Wheat Crop

The dose of nitrogen application and timing are the most important aspects to enhance nitrogen use efficiency and attain high yield. Plant Nitrogen. Wheat crop passes through different growth stages; every stage has a different response to nitrogen. So, it is important to apply it on optimum stage where its efficiency is high. Nitrogen effects on growth heads/sq. Ft, seed/head, grain size and protein percentage in grain ultimately in high yield (Mark, Peter, & Daniel, 2009). During the winter dormancy, wheat plant uses minimum nitrogen if applied more it will be leach down or runoff from the root zone. Stem elongation is the fastest stage of growth. During this phase, a number of grains formation established and rapidly

nitrogen uptake. Improper nitrogen availability during this stage may cause tiller abortion or maybe tiller lost. Proper nitrogen is also needed during this stage to maintain proper leaf area index. Uptake of nitrogen during grain formation is low as compared to stem elongation phase. Nitrogen in plant part is mobilized and transferred to grain, an only a small amount of nitrogen comes from the soil. Research showed that there is no yield enhancement during or after flowering stage, but the foliar application of urea (10-20 lbs. N/acre) enhanced protein contents in grain but not yield. (Mark, Peter, & Daniel, 2009).

Fig. 2 Total biomass and Nitrogen uptake during different growth stages (Brown, Westcott, Christensen, & Pan, 2005)

Wheat Plant required nitrogen on different stages as showing in Fig. 2. The maximum nitrogen uptake can be seen from heading to maturity. So, if there will be the unavailability of proper nitrogen on any stage, it will affect the formation of the next growth stage. Applying of nitrogen on these stages are a very important step. Otherwise, it will cause yield losses. Every stage is related to each other if any growth stage effected by deficiency it will effect to another stage ultimately effect on yield. So, the focus should be on proper dose and timing on the required nitrogen growth stage to provide an adequate amount to plant for better growth and better yield. Due to a shortage of nitrogen plant, will unable to continue its growth and growth will be stunted. Understanding of crop behavior with nitrogen is an important key for any recommendation that varies with variety, soil, region, environmental conditions, etc.

Conclusion:

Application of proper dose on proper time increase nitrogen use efficiency and overall yield of wheat. Availability of nitrogen to plant on required growth stages is an essential aspect. If there will be no nitrogen availability to plant on a specific stage it may cause yield loss; if applied on unessential growth period it will be lost through leaching or run-off ultimately cause an economic loss of farmer. Mostly nitrogen used in grain formation comes from the stem, leaves rather than directly uptake from soil. So, if nitrogen is not available in initial stages of growth ultimately nitrogen use efficiency and yield will be reduced.

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